

Research article

How to measure the robustness and effectiveness of certification schemes and labels in ensuring the sustainability of bio-based products

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ABSTRACT

The rapid proliferation of sustainability certification schemes and labels (CSLs) reflects the rising demand for sustainable products, although the robustness and effectiveness of these certification systems have been increasingly questioned. While CSLs aim to mitigate environmental and socio-economic risks and support responsible market practices, current monitoring systems of CSLs often lack coherence, transparency, and methodological robustness. This study addresses this gap by proposing a conceptual monitoring framework specifically tailored to the bioeconomy, addressing the complexity of global bio-based value chains. Developed through a systematic literature review, a comparative analysis of 26 academic studies and 19 monitoring tools, and stakeholder engagement via interviews and co-creation workshops, the framework introduces a multidimensional structure for evaluating CSLs across three core functions: (I) Building Trust and Transparency, (II) Protecting Sustainability Areas of Concern, and (III) Driving Continuous Improvement. A pilot benchmarking exercise using the Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS) demonstrates the framework's applicability and diagnostic value, revealing both strong alignment in some areas and performance gaps in others—particularly in the economic and circularity dimensions. The framework is designed as a dynamic and modular tool, suitable for use by policymakers, scheme owners, businesses, and consumers. It holds potential to harmonize evaluation practices, guide co-regulatory policy integration, and foster more transparent and credible sustainability certification systems in the bioeconomy meta-sector.

1. Introduction

Global challenges such as climate change, resource depletion, and socio-economic issues—including inequality and poor working conditions—emphasize the urgent need to enhance sustainable production and consumption models across all economic sectors (Sillanpää and Ncibi, 2017). In response, the European Green Deal promotes the transition toward a carbon-neutral and circular economy, endorsing the use of renewable feedstocks for the production of high value-added products (European Commission, 2020). Within this context, the bioeconomy - which utilizes biomass as a primary feedstock - is increasingly recognized as a meta-sector, as it includes a range of different NACE¹ sectors, from agriculture and forestry to bio-based textiles and chemicals (Ronzon et al., 2020). Advancing toward a sustainable circular bioeconomy, particularly one that incorporates the valorization of organic

residues and waste streams, presents significant opportunities for economic growth through innovation and job creation. Simultaneously, it offers a pathway to reduce dependence on non-renewable resources (Ferraz and Pyka, 2023) and contribute meaningfully to the achievement of various Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (Calicioglu and Bogdanski, 2021). Moreover, this transformation addresses critical systemic challenges, such as end-of-life valorization, thereby alleviating environmental pressures and promoting more resilient social and ecological systems (Lokesh et al., 2018).

Achieving a sustainable circular bioeconomy requires not only the balanced use of renewable resources, but also the establishment of regenerative feedstock systems that facilitate reuse and recycling (Aguilar et al., 2019). This transition further depends on the adoption of sustainable practices across all stages of the value chain—including production, processing, marketing, and consumption (Vogelpohl and

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¹ NACE is the acronym for the Statistical Classification of Economic Activities in the European Community.

Töller, 2021), while simultaneously accounting for socio-economic dimensions (Falcone and Imbert, 2019) such as equity, livelihoods, and working conditions (Rebolledo-Leiva et al., 2023). These foundational principles are increasingly supported by evolving regulatory frameworks, notably the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive² (CSRD) and the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive³ (CSDDD), which came into force in 2023 and 2024, respectively. These directives mark a significant shift in corporate accountability by embedding sustainability considerations into business operations and governance structures.

However, despite these advances, a considerable number of actors within bio-based value chains remain outside the scope of these and interlinked regulations. Bridging this regulatory gap necessitates the integration of sustainability principles into emerging bio-based systems (Wurster and Ladu, 2020), also through private governance mechanisms (Ladu and Blind, 2017). In this context, Certification Schemes and Labels (CSLs)⁴ based on Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSSs)—such as the Forest Stewardship Council (FSC)—serve as market-driven tools that play a critical role in monitoring, mitigating and reducing environmental and socio-economic risks (Fernandes Martins et al., 2022). CSLs are increasingly recognized as strategic instruments for advancing sustainable development (Gottinger et al., 2023) and for providing a credible basis to evaluate and communicate the sustainability performance of products (Ladu and Morone, 2024). Importantly, CSLs complement legal frameworks by contributing legitimacy through private transnational governance (Marx et al., 2022). They also facilitate the market adoption of certified bio-based products by enhancing consumer trust and enabling sustainability claims (Morone et al., 2021). Therefore, these transnational tools have become crucial in governing the sustainability of the bioeconomy in fragmented global value chains (Vogelpohl, 2021).

The rapid proliferation of CSLs reflects a growing market demand for sustainable products. However, this expansion has also brought to light several legitimacy and credibility challenges. Scholarly literature points to critical weaknesses, including conflicting priorities and issues of sovereignty in resource-producing countries (Vogelpohl and Töller, 2021), as well as a persistent lack of harmonization in assessment methodologies (Ladu and Morone, 2021). In addition, some schemes exhibit weak verification mechanisms—such as a lack of independent audits (Taylor and Lindenmayer, 2021), and limited coverage of sustainability (Parra-Paitan et al., 2023), and governance dimensions (Tregidga et al., 2019). Further compounding these issues are poorly developed supply chain traceability systems (VanderWilde et al., 2023), which limit transparency and oversight. A related concern is the insufficient ambition of some CSLs to address regulatory gaps, particularly in social and environmental domains. For instance, Partzsch et al. (2019) highlighted that several certification schemes, particularly those involving also active participation from non-governmental organizations (NGOs), may exhibit lower levels of ambition compared to public standards, such as the EU Organic Regulation. Moreover, the growing interest in sustainability certifications has led to an increase in vague, unclear or not well-substantiated industrial claims, including

self-declared certifications. These challenges are strongly interconnected with greenwashing⁵, which creates consumer confusion, erodes trust in CSLs, and raises concerns regarding the quality and credibility of certified products (European Commission, 2023). The current landscape of certification faces significant challenges including information overload (Torma and Thøgersen, 2021); therefore, rather than simplifying decision-making, the proliferation of certifications has contributed to increased disorientation (Dendler, 2014). Indeed, although CSLs were designed to reduce information asymmetries between producers and stakeholders, such as consumers, they often paradoxically exacerbate these disparities (Brenton, 2018), emphasizing the need for simpler and transparent tools for eradicating asymmetric information (Nikolaou and Kazantzidis, 2016).

Within this context, benchmarking and monitoring systems for CSLs have emerged as critical instruments for enhancing transparency and accountability. Tools such as the ITC Standards Map are widely recognized for their capacity to provide stakeholders—including policy-makers, businesses, and consumers—with systematic insights into the characteristics, governance structures, and performance of diverse CSLs (Mori Junior et al., 2016). In addition, a growing body of research has developed analytical frameworks to facilitate the comparative assessment of CSLs across sectors, enabling structured evaluations based on governance, sustainability criteria, and verification processes (Boev and van Gelder, 2023; da Silva Júnior et al., 2016; Depoorter and Marx, 2024; McDermott, 2013; Nikolaou and Tsalis, 2018; Rector et al., 2023; Tröster and Hiete, 2018). In parallel, some studies have introduced scoring systems designed to rank schemes based on their attributes and coverage, thereby supporting consumers in making more informed and sustainable purchasing decisions (Nikolaou and Kazantzidis, 2016). Moreover, monitoring practices have been embedded within benchmarking exercises that assess certification schemes against predefined sustainability criteria, offering structured and comparative assessments of scheme robustness and comprehensiveness (Bonisoli et al., 2019; Presley and Meade, 2010).

In the specific context of the bioeconomy, an emerging body of literature has investigated the application and effectiveness of CSLs in bio-based value chains. These studies have often focused on schemes operating in specific sectors and/or geographical regions, evaluating their effectiveness and adaptability, as well as responsiveness to local socio-environmental contexts (Gutierrez Garzon et al., 2020; Partzsch et al., 2019; Osmundsen et al., 2020; Vogelpohl, 2023). Additionally, benchmarking exercises have been employed to assess the alignment of these schemes with a range of sustainability principles and performance indicators (Boev and van Gelder, 2023; Bracco et al., 2019). Despite this progress, a significant knowledge gap remains: there is still no comprehensive monitoring system specifically tailored to the complexity and diversity of bio-based sectors and value chains. Such a system is essential for ensuring that certification schemes effectively support the integration of sustainability principles across the bioeconomy and contribute meaningfully to its governance and development.

Against this background, this study addresses the central research question: *How should a monitoring framework be designed, and which key elements should it incorporate, to effectively assess the robustness and effectiveness of certification schemes and labels within the bio-based industry?* To answer this, the study first identified and reviewed existing monitoring systems, providing a comprehensive overview of the methodologies currently used to benchmark and compare CSLs, along with their key features and characteristics. Building on the findings from the analysis of the selected tools and studies, a conceptual framework with

² The full regulation on corporate sustainability reporting can be found at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32022L2464>.

³ More information on CSDDD can be found at: https://commission.europa.eu/business-economy-euro/doing-business-eu/sustainability-due-diligence-responsible-business/corporate-sustainability-due-diligence_en.

⁴ Different terms are used in the literature to describe voluntary sustainability certifications, including: Certification Schemes and Labels (CSLs), Voluntary Sustainability Standards (VSSs) (Marx et al., 2022, Fernandes Martins, et al., 2022); Voluntary Sustainability Programs (VSPs) (Schleifer et al., 2019); Certification Programs (Gutierrez Garzon et al., 2020); Voluntary sustainability commitments (Parra-Paitan et al., 2023) and Eco-labels (Zielinski and Botero, 2015; van der Ven, 2019). While all these terms refer to a similar concept, in the present study we refer to CSLs as a standardized approach.

⁵ Greenwashing refers to the practice of disseminating misleading information by overstating a product's sustainability performance or through false claims of its environmental benefits with the aim of creating a responsible public image (Nemes et al., 2022).

its core functions and key principles was proposed. Finally, the applicability of the proposed framework was demonstrated through a practical example, and recommendations were provided for its future refinement and use.

The remainder of this article is structured as follows: Section 2 outlines the adopted four-step methodological approach. Section 3 presents the results of the systematic literature review and the in-depth analysis of existing monitoring systems. This section also introduces the proposed concept and key principles of the monitoring framework and demonstrates its applicability through a benchmarking exercise. Section 4 discusses the results and explores their practical implementation. Finally, Section 5 draws conclusions and outlines the broader implications of the study's findings.

2. Methodology

As depicted in Fig. 1, the methodology follows a four-step approach: (1) Systematic literature review - identifying and selecting relevant existing monitoring systems used to assess CSLs; (2) Analysis of selected monitoring tools - examining their key features, characteristics, and methodologies to identify essential components that a monitoring system should include; (3) Conceptualization of a monitoring framework tailored to the context of bio-based products - defining its key functions, core principles, and structural elements; and (4) Demonstration of the framework's applicability - applying the framework in a benchmarking exercise to assess its practical relevance and derive recommendations for future use and development.

Step 1 Systematic Literature review

A systematic review was conducted to identify and select existing monitoring systems and relevant methodological approaches for benchmarking and assessing certification schemes and labels (CSLs). The review encompassed both peer-reviewed academic publications and grey literature - including tools and reports from industry, governmental, and non-governmental organizations. The scope extended beyond bio-based systems to ensure a comprehensive understanding of monitoring approaches.

Following the PRISMA guidelines (Moher et al., 2009, 2015), the review followed a four-step process: Identification, Screening, Eligibility and Inclusion (Fig. 2). Using the Web of Science database, keywords related to monitoring systems and CSLs were applied. Initial searches with "monitoring system AND certification schemes" and "monitoring system AND labels" yielded 16,630 results. To refine results, the term "labels" was substituted with "ecolabels", reducing results significantly. Searches restricted to the period between 2010 and 2022 resulted in 209 publications, which were further reduced to 148 after removing duplicates. To ensure relevance in the final sample, the publications had to meet three criteria: (I) focus on the monitoring, benchmarking, or assessment of sustainability certification schemes and labels; (II) comparative analysis of at least two certification schemes or labels; (III) assessment of sustainability-related aspects. As a result, 26 studies were selected for qualitative synthesis (Table 1).

The grey literature review followed similar search principles and incorporated keywords such as *monitoring certification schemes*, *monitoring systems*, and *benchmarking tool*, combined with the search strings: *sustainability*, *sustainability certification schemes*, *labels*. This was complemented by reviewing existing EU projects' databases. A preliminary list of relevant monitoring tools was refined with input from stakeholders, including discussions with representatives from the International Social and Environmental Accreditation and Labelling Alliance

(ISEAL Alliance).⁶ The search yielded 23 results, from which 19 monitoring tools were selected for further evaluation, following the exclusion of ineligible records.

A smaller set of tools was shortlisted for in-depth analysis based on the following criteria: *coverage* (representing a broad range of CSLs and value chain stages), *comprehensiveness* (inclusion of governance, operational, and sustainability aspects and impacts), *interpretation approach* (use of accessible and representative result visualization), *target audience* (relevance of diverse stakeholders, including policymakers and scheme owners), and *assessment frequency* (indication of ongoing monitoring or one-time assessment).

A total of 19 monitoring systems were evaluated and scored on a scale from 0 to 2, with '0' - indicating not suitable, '1' - partially suitable, and '2' - suitable (see Appendix A-Table S1). The scoring, based on publicly available data and expert opinion, identified the ITC Standards Map and Siegelklarheit as the highest-scoring tools (8 points each), followed by the GSSI Global Benchmark Tool, FEFAC Responsible Soy Benchmarking Tool, SME Compass, and FSI Basket of Standards (7 points each). These six tools were selected to further in-depth analysis.

Step 2 Analysis of the identified studies and selected monitoring tools

In the second step, the 26 academic studies and 6 selected monitoring tools were analyzed to identify features and characteristics commonly used for benchmarking and comparing CSLs. The analysis focused on the methodologies, structures, scoring mechanisms, and approaches to visual representation used in the tools.

To enhance the robustness of the analysis and address potential data gaps, direct engagement with the tool developers and system owners was pursued. In collaboration with ISEAL, four online consultations were conducted with representatives of the ITC Standards Map, Siegelklarheit, FEFAC Responsible Soy Benchmarking Tool, and SME Compass. Between mid-May and mid-July 2023, a total of four interviews were conducted. For the FSI Basket of Standards and GSSI Global Benchmark Tool, insights were gathered through email correspondence due to limited availability for interviews. These exchanges provided updated information on tool design, usability, and practical application, thereby strengthening the foundation for developing the monitoring framework.

Step 3 Conceptualization of the monitoring framework

Drawing on insights from Steps 1 and 2, a tailored monitoring framework for assessing CSLs in the bio-based sector was conceptualized. This process was guided by best practices outlined in the ISEAL Sustainability Benchmarking Good Practice Guide (ISEAL, 2020) (Fig. 3), and was further complemented by the findings of Tröster and Hiete (2018) and the ISEAL Credibility Principles (ISEAL, 2021).

This step involved several sub-steps: first, identifying the target audience and clarifying the primary purpose of the monitoring framework; second, determining the key elements of the framework, including principles related to robustness and sustainability; and third, developing an evaluation structure designed to support the framework's intended purpose. Operational and governance principles were drawn from existing policies, standards, monitoring tools and third-party certification systems. Particular emphasis was placed on the operational requirements of the ITC Standards Map due to its extensive indicator coverage and alignment with ISEAL benchmarking principles. The sustainability dimension was further shaped by recent research, notably the work of Ares-Sainz et al. (2025), which informed the identification and structuring of relevant sustainability indicators for bio-based products.

⁶ ISEAL is a global membership organization working with sustainability standards and certification systems focusing on good practices to support sustainability systems.

Fig. 1. Methodological approach. Source: Authors' own elaboration

Fig. 2. PRISMA flow diagram for the systematic literature review on existing sustainability monitoring system. Source: Authors' own elaboration based on Moher et al. (2009).

The initial framework concept was further refined through stakeholder validation. Feedback was collected during two co-creation workshops, held in January and May 2023 as part of the EU-funded STAR4BBS⁷ project. Participants included certification scheme owners, researchers, monitoring experts, and policymakers, whose insights informed both the framework's structure and the usability features of the proposed framework.

Step 4 Demonstration of framework's applicability

To validate the relevance and practicality of the proposed monitoring framework, a demonstration benchmarking exercise was

conducted. This pilot application involved testing the framework against an established sustainability certification scheme—the Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS). This scheme was selected due to its relevance to the bioeconomy, particularly its broad use within the textile sector, its comprehensive sustainability scope, and adherence to high governance standards. Moreover, this scheme incorporates not only a Business-to-Business (B2B) approach—but also a well-established Business-to-Consumer (B2C) strategy through a well-recognized labeling system.

The benchmarking exercise applied the framework's principles and evaluation structure to the GOTS' system, assessing its performance across the three-tiered structure: *Building Trust and Transparency*, *Protecting Sustainability Areas of Concern*, and *Driving Continuous Improvement*. The process began with a pre-assessment questionnaire designed to evaluate both the applicability and the extent of coverage for each principle, aiming to provide a better understanding of the scheme's scope and focus areas. Following the guidance provided in the Instructions tab of Appendix B, the template was completed by specifying the name of the certification scheme, relevant feedstock type(s), applicable value chain actor(s), and reference sources for each applicable

⁷ Co-creation workshops "Prioritization of Sustainability Policy Targets for Certification Schemes and Labels" on 26th January 2023 (online) and "Validation of the relevant pre-selected sustainability certification schemes and labels" on 26th May 2023 (online) were organized within the EU Horizon funded project STAR4BBS (<https://star4bbs.eu/>).

Table 1
Selected studies from scientific literature.

Authors	Article Title
Kadam et al. (2021)	Mapping convergence of sustainable forest management systems: Comparing three protocols and two certification schemes for ascertaining the trends in global forest governance
Ali et al. (2021)	Establishing a Green Building Certification Scheme and Standards for Multifamily Residential Buildings: Case of Jordan
Kittinger et al. (2021)	Applying a jurisdictional approach to support sustainable seafood
Gutierrez Garzon et al. (2020)	A Comparative Analysis of Five Forest Certification Programs
Olawumi et al. (2020)	Development of a building sustainability assessment method (BSAM) for developing countries in sub-Saharan Africa
Mussells and Stephenson (2020)	A comparison of sustainability objectives: how well does the Canadian Fisheries Research Network framework compare with fisheries, forestry, and aquaculture certification schemes?
Tröster and Hiete (2019)	Do voluntary sustainability certification schemes in the sector of mineral resources meet stakeholder demands? A multi-criteria decision analysis
Partzsch et al. (2019)	Cotton certification in Sub-Saharan Africa: Promotion of environmental sustainability or greenwashing?
Mai-Moulin et al. (2019)	Toward a harmonization of national sustainability requirements and criteria for solid biomass
Chkanikova and Kogg (2018)	Sustainability governance service providers: the role of third-party product certification in facilitating corporate life cycle management
Sugiura and Oki (2018)	Reasons for Choosing Forest Stewardship Council (FSC) and Sustainable Green Ecosystem Council (SGEC) Schemes and the Effects of Certification Acquisition by Forestry Enterprises in Japan
Mengistie et al. (2017)	Governance of agro pesticide through private environmental and social standards in the global cut flower chain from Ethiopia
Montazeri et al. (2016)	Meta-Analysis of Life Cycle Energy and Greenhouse Gas Emissions for Priority Biobased Chemicals
Hazen et al. (2016)	Translating sustainable seafood frameworks to assess the implementation of ecosystem-based fisheries management
Trusty et al. (2016)	Statistical tools to assess the breadth and depth of shrimp aquaculture certification schemes
Barnett (2016)	An evaluation of the UK's use of SFM standards to procure solid woody biomass for electricity generation using sustainable bioenergy criteria
Zielinski and Botero (2015)	Are eco-labels sustainable? Beach certification schemes in Latin America and the Caribbean
Chiputwa et al. (2015)	Food Standards, Certification, and Poverty among Coffee Farmers in Uganda
Chaplin-Kramer et al. (2015)	Ecosystem service information to benefit sustainability standards for commodity supply chains
Englund and Berndes, 2016	How do sustainability standards consider biodiversity?
Schut and Florin (2015)	The policy and practice of sustainable biofuels: Between global frameworks and local heterogeneity. The case of food security in Mozambique
Sikkema et al. (2014)	Legal Harvesting, Sustainable Sourcing and Cascaded Use of Wood for Bioenergy: Their Coverage through Existing Certification Frameworks for Sustainable Forest Management
Meyer and Priess (2014)	Indicators of bioenergy-related certification schemes - An analysis of the quality and comprehensiveness for assessing local/regional environmental impacts
Young et al. (2014)	Prospects for sustainability certification of metals
Lee (2013)	A comprehensive review of metrics of building environmental assessment schemes
Merger et al. (2011)	Options for REDD plus Voluntary Certification to Ensure Net GHG Benefits, Poverty Alleviation, Sustainable Management of Forests and Biodiversity Conservation

principle. The level of coverage was categorized as full, partial, or absent. In the case that a feedstock, value chain actor or principle is considered out of scope, the corresponding principles were marked as not applicable.

3. Results

3.1. Results of the scientific literature review

The systematic literature review identified 26 relevant academic studies (see Table 1), which varied considerably in terms of scope, purpose, and methodological approach. To better interpret this heterogeneity, the studies were categorized into three analytical groups based on their primary objectives and methods: benchmarking studies (10), comparison studies (10), and relationship exploration studies (6), as summarized in Table 2.

All three types of studies involved data collection, data analysis, and results interpretation. The summary of this analysis is provided in Appendix A – Table S2. In terms of data collection methods, studies in the *benchmarking* assessment group primarily used desk research, online questionnaires, and comparative analysis of life cycle assessment (LCA) studies. The *comparison* assessment group focused on comparing different CSLs in terms of consistency and changes in categorization (e.g. principles, criteria, indicators), utilizing a wide range of data collection methods, including expert surveys, structured and semi-structured questionnaires, interviews, and literature reviews. Lastly, the *exploring a relationship* assessment group relied mainly on interviews and surveys.

All assessment types employed various data analysis techniques to evaluate sustainability standards and/or certification schemes and labels. These techniques included both qualitative and quantitative methods, such as categorization analysis, content analysis, statistical tests, and data visualization tools. In *benchmarking* assessments, studies applied analytical methods like categorization analysis, multi-criteria decision analysis, and detailed content analysis. They also used statistical techniques, including ANCOVA, ANOVA, MANOVA, and the Restricted Maximum Likelihood approach (REML). In *comparative* assessments, studies primarily utilized qualitative analysis, descriptive comparisons, and comparative cross-case analysis, with a few incorporating more specific methods, like the Delphi technique, Analytic Hierarchy Process, and score-weighting (e.g., credit points). Finally, in *exploring a relationship* assessments, studies relied on descriptive comparisons, propensity score matching, and case study approaches.

Data interpretation involves the presentation and analysis of results, assessing their clarity, transparency, and relevance to the intended audience of the tool. This layer also includes the visualization of results, illustrating how information can be accessed and effectively communicated to users. In *benchmarking* assessments, the evaluation of result representation and interpretation prominently featured methods such as direct rating, color-coding tables, scoring charts, and relative ordinal ranking systems, which facilitate comparisons of how different schemes consider specific criteria or principles. These methods allow for clear comparisons among schemes and help identify their strengths and weaknesses. In *comparative* assessments, result interpretation was less extensive and employed graphical representations like Sankey diagrams, radar diagrams, pie charts, criteria ranking, and sub-attribute classification. These methods were more focused on identifying the contribution of different indicators to the overall sustainability performance of a single scheme, rather than comparing how schemes perform relative to each other. Finally, *exploring the relationship* assessments were largely descriptive, focusing on summarizing and comparing results from different studies through tabular comparisons, descriptive analysis, and summary statistics. These assessments were more focused on presenting the relationship between variables and evaluating the impact of sustainability certification schemes and labels.

3.2. Results of the analysis of selected monitoring tools

As summarized in Tables 3 and 4, the six selected monitoring

Fig. 3. Steps in the benchmarking process recommended in the ISEAL’s Sustainability Benchmarking Good Practice Guide. Source: ISEAL, 2020.

systems—ITC Standards Map, Siegelklarheit,⁸ GSSI Global Benchmark Tool,⁹ FEFAC Responsible Soy Benchmarking Tool¹⁰, SME Compass,¹¹ and FSI Basket of Standards¹²—serve distinct but complementary purposes in evaluating sustainability standards, certification schemes and labels.

The detailed objectives, key characteristics, and result interpretations of each monitoring system are presented in Table 4.

Most of these tools were developed to promote and ensure credibility, consistency, and effectiveness of CSLs. Their objectives include building trust among stakeholders—such as consumers, companies, and public authorities—and facilitating the transition towards more sustainable and responsible production and consumption practices. While their goals are aligned, each tool operates within a distinct scope and sectoral focus. The FEFAC Responsible Soy Benchmarking Tool is geared towards identifying soy certification schemes that meet European feed industry requirements for responsible soy production, while Siegelklarheit aims to provide clarity and enable users to make informed decisions for sustainable consumption based on credible labels. The ITC Standards Map functions as an extensive information platform, offering detailed insights into sustainability standards and certification schemes. SME Compass is designed to guide companies in identifying and managing sustainability risks in their supply chains. The FSI Basket of Standards supports responsible sourcing within the floriculture sector by showcasing schemes that meet Good Agricultural Practices (GAP), environmental, and social criteria. Lastly, the GSSI Global Benchmark Tool provides formal recognition to seafood certification schemes that successfully complete the benchmark process.

The tools also differ in their structural and methodological characteristics. The ITC Standards Map offers a comprehensive overview of sustainability standards and certification schemes, covering various

⁸ Siegelklarheit (<https://www.siegelklarheit.de/en/>) is an initiative by the Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) that focuses on increasing transparency and clarity in the landscape of sustainability standards and labels.

⁹ The GSSI Global Benchmark Tool (<https://www.ourgssi.org/benchmarking/>) is an assessment framework developed by the Global Sustainable Seafood Initiative (GSSI). It evaluates the sustainability of seafood certification schemes and standards worldwide.

¹⁰ The FEFAC Responsible Soy Benchmarking Tool (<https://sustainabilitygateway.org/european-feed-manufacturers-federation-fefac-soy-benchmarking-tool/>) is a comprehensive tool developed by FEFAC (European Feed Manufacturers’ Federation) to assess and evaluate the sustainability of soy production and sourcing practices.

¹¹ SME Compass (<https://wirtschaft-entwicklung.de/en/helpdesk-on-business-human-rights/sme-compass/>) is an online platform that assists companies in enhancing the sustainability of their supply chains by establishing robust management systems.

¹² The FSI Basket of Standards (<https://www.fsi2025.com/basket/>), developed by the Floriculture Sustainability Initiative (FSI), is a tool designed to advance responsible sourcing practices in the floral industry, focusing on environmental and social aspects.

Table 2

Classification based on the adopted approaches and methodology.

Assessment type	Description	Identified studies
Benchmarking	Studies assessing existing CSLs against specific criteria or indicators, such as ecological, governance, and socio-economic aspects. They employ various methods, including desk research, online questionnaires, and various statistical analysis for assessing performance.	Mussells and Stephenson (2020); Tröster and Hiete, 2019; Partzsch et al., (2019); Montazeri et al., (2016); Tlusty et al., (2016); Zielinski and Botero (2015); Englund and Berndes, 2016; Sikkema et al., (2014); Meyer and Priess (2014); Merger et al., (2011)
Comparing	Studies performing comparative analyses, either between certification standards/schemes themselves or against certain aspects of those schemes, or even comparing a certification system with other rating tools. They utilize various data collection methods, such as expert surveys, structured and semi-structured questionnaires, interviews, and literature reviews.	Kadam et al., (2021); Ali et al., (2021); Gutierrez Garzon et al., (2020); Olawumi et al., (2019); Chkanikova and Kogg (2018); Hazen et al., (2016); Barnett (2016); Young et al. (2014); Lee (2013)
Exploring a relationship	Studies exploring different type of relationships among certain elements, e.g. they investigate the relationship between two or more variables or systems, or the impact of certification on environment, livelihoods, etc.	Kittinger et al., (2021); Sugiura and Oki (2018); Mengistie et al., (2017); Chiputwa et al., (2015); Chaplin-Kramer et al., (2015); Schut and Florin (2015)

sustainability topics through 1.650 indicators. Rather than scoring or rating schemes, it documents the presence (or absence) of relevant criteria within the standards being compared. Siegelklarheit uses the SSCT (Sustainability Standards Comparison Tool) methodology to evaluate and compare labels across product groups. The GSSI Global Benchmark Tool assesses certification schemes based on performance areas such as scheme governance, operational management, and standards for aquaculture and fisheries certification. The FEFAC Responsible Soy Benchmarking Tool evaluates certification schemes against specific criteria outlined in FEFAC’s Soy Sourcing Guidelines. SME Compass benchmarks certification and participation standards against 40 due diligence criteria derived from the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights (UNGP). The FSI Basket of Standards evaluates compliance with Good Agricultural Practices (GAP), as well as environmental and/or social requirements, offering guidance for responsible sourcing and production practices within the flowers and plants supply chain.

Differences were also observed in how these tools present and interpret their assessment results. The ITC Standards Map visualizes

Table 3
Summary of the commonalities and differences among reviewed monitoring systems.

Aspect	Commonalities	Differences
Objectives	Assessing different schemes and labels for transparency, credibility, and sustainability in various industries.	Tailored to specific industries or product groups, with sector-specific criteria and methodologies.
Key Characteristics	Using comprehensive databases to collect and analyze data and relying on structured criteria related to sustainable and responsible practices.	Depth of benchmarks and assessment methods vary, including scoring and comparison approaches.
Results Interpretation	Enabling criteria comparisons via matrices or frameworks, with a predominance of qualitative assessments.	Results range from pass/fail to detailed scoring systems, visualized using graphs, matrices, or reports.

Table 4
Overview of the main features of selected monitoring tools.

Tool	Objectives	Key Characteristics	Results Interpretation
ITC Standards Map	Provides requirements of standards for environmental and social protection, economic development, quality and food safety, and business ethics.	Covers more than 300 sustainability standards and certification schemes, including system characteristics and sustainability topics through 1650 indicators.	It documents the presence of related criteria within the standard. Results visualized using pie charts and tables.
Siegelklarheit	Enables users to compare standards and labels within product groups (e.g. textiles and paper).	Uses ITC data with its own SSCT (Sustainability Standards Comparison Tool) -based evaluation methodology.	3-star rating system to consumers (B2C) with a 0–2 point scoring scale.
GSSI Global Benchmark Tool	Recognizes seafood certification schemes that meet benchmark criteria.	Benchmarks governance, operational management, and aquaculture/fisheries standards.	Uses an Excel-based framework; results published as benchmark reports.
FEFAC Responsible Soy Benchmarking Tool	Identifies soy certification schemes meeting European feed industry requirements for responsible soy production.	Benchmarks schemes against 73 criteria in FEFAC Soy Sourcing Guidelines.	Pass/fail system; successful schemes marked "FEFAC benchmarked" in ITC Standards Map.
SME Compass	Helps companies manage social and environmental risks in supply chains.	Benchmarks against 40 due diligence criteria (UNGP (United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights)-based).	Results displayed as percentage bars for up to 4 standards.
FSI Basket of Standards	Promotes responsible sourcing in flowers and plants supply chains.	Assesses compliance with GAP (Good Agricultural Practices), GSCP (Global Social Compliance Programme)/SSCI (Sustainable Supply Chain Initiative) standards.	Successful standards added to the publicly accessible FSI Basket.

information using tables, pie charts, and summary graphs that reflect the level of criteria coverage. This format supports a comparative understanding of how standards address different sustainability dimensions. SME Compass compares up to four standards simultaneously, visualizing the results as percentage bars using the ITC Data Entry Tool. The FEFAC Responsible Soy Benchmarking Tool displays schemes that meet the criteria as 'FEFAC benchmarked' within the ITC Standards Map, adopting a straightforward pass/fail system. Siegelklarheit interprets results through a three-star rating system, enabling the audience to discern between various labels and their sustainability performance. By assigning stars based on predefined criteria, it simplifies the interpretation process and allows stakeholders to quickly grasp the sustainability performance of certification schemes, standards, or supply chains. It uses a point system or a joint consideration of individual dimension ratings to provide an overall rating ranging from "Not assessed" (for schemes not fulfilling minimum requirements) to "Good choice!" or "Very good choice!" (GIZ Sustainability Standards Comparison Tool [SSCT] within Siegelklarheit). The FSI Basket of Standards acknowledges successfully benchmarked standards, adding them to the FSI Basket, and making them publicly available for consultation and comparison. The GSSI Global Benchmark Tool utilizes an Excel-based Global Benchmark Framework, publicly announcing recognized certification schemes on their website along with a benchmark report.

3.3. Conceptualization of the monitoring system framework for bio-based value chains

The findings derived from the previous sections, particularly the analysis of six existing monitoring systems (Section 3.2) and the key recommendations from ISEAL’s Sustainability Benchmarking Good Practice Guide (2020), have directly informed the conceptualization of a tailored monitoring framework for bio-based value chains. This conceptual model has been designed to address the specific challenges and dynamics of certification schemes and labels (CSLs) in the bioeconomy by integrating relevant learnings into a structured, three-phase

development process: Phase 1 - identifying the purpose and target audience, Phase 2 – determining the core elements to be included, and Phase 3 - developing the appropriate evaluation structure designed to support the framework’s intended purpose.

Phase 1 Identifying the purpose and target audience

Clearly articulating the purpose of the monitoring system and identifying its intended audience is a critical first step, as these factors shape its content, evaluation structure, and the way results are communicated. For instance, Siegelklarheit aims to support consumers in making informed purchasing decisions, while GSSI and FEFAC address industry-specific benchmarking needs. Drawing on the findings presented in Sections 3.1 and 3.2, the primary aim of the proposed monitoring framework applicable to bio-based systems is to assess the effectiveness and robustness of existing certification schemes and labels (CSLs).

The main target audiences for this conceptualized framework include European policymakers and sustainability certification scheme owners. The monitoring framework is designed to inform EU policymakers about how existing CSLs contribute to EU sustainability targets in the bioeconomy, while also encouraging scheme owners to improve and align their systems with these goals. Additionally, the framework may be of significant value to companies operating in complex bio-based value chains. To achieve this, the monitoring framework must provide functionalities that meet the specific needs of these audiences.

Phase 2 Determining the core elements of the monitoring framework

The second step involves defining the key assessment elements. This includes selecting the relevant aspects of CSLs to be evaluated and defining the specific information to be collected and analyzed. The reviewed tools exhibited various strategies for organizing their assessments—some emphasizing governance (e.g. ITC, GSSI), others focusing on sustainability indicators (e.g. SME Compass, Siegelklarheit), and a few addressing long-term effectiveness (e.g. FSI, partially GSSI).

Drawing from these varied practices, the proposed framework consolidates these dimensions into three interconnected levels: operational requirements (i.e., system), sustainability performance (i.e., content), and the long-term effectiveness (i.e., outcomes) of CSLs.

As illustrated in Fig. 4, the assessment principles incorporated into the monitoring system are clustered into three functional levels, that correspond to distinct monitoring objectives: **Function I: Building Trust and Transparency** (focuses on evaluating the robustness and credibility of CSLs); **Function II: Protecting Sustainability Areas of Concern** (focuses on examining the critical sustainability issues covered by the schemes); and **Function III: Driving Continuous Improvement** (focuses on assessing the impact of CSLs over time).

Within each of the three functions outlined in Fig. 4, a set of key assessment principles has been identified based on the analysis of existing CSLs and monitoring tools. For Function I, the principles include governance and scheme management, standard setting, assurance, and claims and traceability—elements crucial for ensuring transparency and structural robustness. Function II incorporates sustainability indicators reflecting the environmental, social, economic, and circular dimensions, which are central to evaluating the substantive coverage of sustainability concerns. In Function III, the focus is placed on assessing the impacts of certification schemes, and monitoring and evaluation, for driving improvement over time. These elements were not selected arbitrarily but emerged from a systematic synthesis of features and methodologies identified in the reviewed monitoring systems, ensuring their relevance and applicability to bio-based contexts. The structure and content of this framework, therefore, provide a targeted and evidence-based foundation for assessing CSLs, with the ultimate goal of supporting alignment with EU sustainability targets and informing both policy and scheme development.

More specifically, Function I emphasizes the operational characteristics of certification schemes and labels, focusing on requirements related to governance, performance, legal compliance, traceability, and implementation mechanisms (e.g., audits, verification, and certification). The indicators at this level assess the overall procedures governing the certification, including the rules and procedures for implementation and evaluation. This function ensures the credibility and reliability of certification systems by verifying adherence to systemic requirements and effectively monitoring the chain of custody. Additionally, it incorporates features that enhance stakeholder acceptance, such as the involvement of different stakeholders in the governance (Marx, 2014) and the transparency of the CSLs (Auld and Gulbrandsen, 2010). Table 5 presents the key principles selected under Function I: Building Trust and Transparency. These were derived from an in-depth review of the structural components of existing CSLs and established monitoring tools,

Table 5
Key principles grouped under four assessment categories within Function I: Building Trust and Transparency.

Category	Principle
Governance and Scheme management	Scheme scope and objectives
	Governance structure
	Stakeholder participation
	Due diligence
Standard setting	Complaints and dispute resolution mechanism
	Standards content
	Standard-setting process
	Standards consultation
Assurance	Assurance system
	Conformity assessment
	Conformity assessment bodies
	Auditing
Traceability and claims	Oversight mechanism
	Chain of Custody traceability system
	Claims and products labelling policy
	Consequences of misuse of claims
	Minimum percentage claims

and are grouped into four assessment categories: standard setting, assurance, traceability and claims, and governance and scheme management.

Function II focuses on the sustainability requirements of CSLs in alignment with EU policies and targets, addressing different pillars of sustainability: environmental, social, economic, and circular. Each pillar encompasses a set of key principles that reflect critical sustainability concerns, identified through the comparative review of existing schemes and monitoring tools, and informed by the indicators proposed by Ares-Sainz et al. (2025). Environmental principles cover topics such as air pollution, forest practices, soil quality, water resources, biodiversity conservation, and climate change. Social principles address issues including workers’ rights, community well-being, fair competition and transparency towards consumers. Economic indicators evaluate aspects linked to profitability, long-term investments, productivity and risk assessment. Circularity indicators focus on measuring the extent to which certified products or feedstock contribute to circularity, product design, end-of-life and resource efficiency. Table 6 outlines the key principles grouped under each sustainability pillar that form the foundation for evaluating the substantive content of CSLs (see Table 7).

Accurate data collection is crucial for measuring and tracking sustainability impacts over time and evaluating the long-term effectiveness of CSLs. Function III focuses on assessing these impacts, ensuring that certification systems not only meet initial benchmarks but also demonstrate ongoing progress. This function emphasizes the importance

Fig. 4. Conceptual framework for monitoring CSLs within the bioeconomy.
Source: Authors’ own elaboration

Table 6

Key principles grouped under four pillars within Function II: Protecting Sustainability Areas of Concern.

Pillar	Principle
Environmental	Climate change
	Air quality
	Water quality and conservation
	Soil management
	Biodiversity protection
	Natural resources
	Hazardous substances
Social	Workers' rights
	Wellbeing of consumers
	Wellbeing of the local community
	Society
Economic	Financial viability and profitability
	Long-term investment
	Fair business practices
	Risk management
Circular	Products and material design
	Production processes
	Circular transition
	Waste management

Table 7

Key principles grouped under two categories within Function III: Driving Continuous Improvement.

Category	Principle
Scheme impacts	Strategies for achieving impacts
	Measurable progress
Monitoring and evaluation	Monitoring and evaluation (M&E) system
	Learning and continuous improvement

of collecting feedback from key stakeholders, including supply chain actors, scheme owners, NGOs, and consumers. By integrating stakeholder insights, it provides a comprehensive understanding of the certification's real-world performance, fostering continuous improvement and ensuring alignment with sustainability goals over time. Table 7 presents the key principles associated with Function III, grouped under two main categories: scheme impacts and monitoring and evaluation. These principles reflect essential components for understanding how certification schemes monitor, validate, and advance their measurable progress and improvement.

Phase 3 Developing the evaluation structure

The third phase focuses on designing the evaluation structure for the monitoring framework, which determines how the data collected for each CSL will be analyzed and assessed to fulfill the benchmark's defined purpose. To guide this process, four basic evaluation models are proposed in ISEAL's Sustainability Benchmarking Good Practice Guide (ISEAL, 2020) (see Table 8): Threshold, Improvement, Ranking, and Peer comparison. The benchmark should clearly define a minimum set of performance requirements that reflect the convenor's expectations. The benchmarking process should be rigorous enough to ascertain whether the entities being benchmarked meet this defined performance threshold.

A robust evaluation structure is essential to determine whether the assessed certification schemes meet or exceed this baseline. While each model brings distinct advantages and limitations, thoughtful selection and tailoring of these approaches—through the integration of system-specific functionalities and clear guiding principles—can help mitigate potential shortcomings. As part of the stakeholder validation process and the co-creation workshops held during the development of the monitoring framework, scheme owners were engaged through a Mentimeter survey to indicate their preferred benchmarking model. The majority expressed a preference for the Threshold and Improvement

Table 8

ISEAL Benchmarking models (ISEAL, 2020) and selected corresponding benchmarking tools.

Model	Purpose	Key features	Benchmarking tool
	To qualify entities that meet or exceed a common baseline or threshold. Can have different incentives: often used for recognition.	Performance bar set at the level of acceptable practice.	FEFAC Responsible Soy Benchmarking Tool Siegelklarheit ITC Standards Map GSSI (partly) FSI Basket of Standards
	To encourage improved practices by showing progress toward good practice.	Aspirational performance bar set beyond current practice to provide direction and incentive.	FEFAC (partly) SME Compass GSSI (partly)
	To compare performance of similar entities through a ranked evaluation.	Entities are scored against performance topics and compared.	Siegelklarheit (partly)
	To conduct an internal comparison of an entity's own performance against its peers	The reference benchmark is the practices of the benchmarking entity itself. Examples are not readily shared.	ITC Standards Map (partly)

models, or a hybrid combination of both. This feedback reinforces the relevance of these approaches for the CSL context, suggesting that a model which balances minimum performance requirements with incentives for progressive enhancement is both practical and widely accepted by key stakeholders.

3.4. Demonstration of the proposed monitoring framework's applicability

The results of the analysis assessing the applicability of the monitoring framework through benchmarking against the Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS) are presented in Appendix B. This benchmarking exercise aimed to test how well the framework's three functional components—Function I: *Building Trust and Transparency*, Function II: *Protecting Sustainability Areas of Concern*, and Function III: *Driving Continuous Improvement*—aligned with the operational and sustainability characteristics of an established certification scheme.

Fig. 5. Applicability of framework principles to the Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS).

As shown in Fig. 5, the applicability of the framework's principles varied across its three functions. In Function I, all 17 principles were found to be applicable, indicating that GOTS covers the full breadth of governance, assurance, and transparency topics included in the framework.

In contrast, for Function II, only 9 of the 19 principles were considered applicable, while 10 were marked as not applicable—likely reflecting the bio-based sector specific nature of some principles. Many economic and circularity-related indicators within Function II are more relevant to sector-specific or specialized schemes and thus fall outside GOTS's specific mandate. The applicability results serve to contextualize the coverage assessment, ensuring that only principles relevant to the scope of the certification scheme are evaluated.

Under Function III, all 4 principles were found to be applicable, reflecting the scheme's stated commitment to long-term performance evaluation, impact assessment, and adaptive learning. The results indicate a strong foundation in monitoring and evaluation practices, with clear mechanisms for iterative learning. Nonetheless, there are opportunities to strengthen the scheme's approach to measurable progress and the integration of dynamic feedback processes.

The coverage results for all applicable principles (Fig. 6) provide a more nuanced picture of how comprehensively GOTS meets the framework's expectations. Within Function I, 13 out of 17 principles were fully covered, and 4 were partially covered, indicating robust mechanisms in place for standard-setting process, scheme management, and labelling policy. This outcome reinforces GOTS's credibility in governance and its compliance with high assurance and oversight principles.

In Function II, the limited applicability of principles naturally resulted in a smaller sample for evaluation. Of the 9 applicable principles, 5 were fully addressed, 3 were partially addressed, and 1 was not covered. While GOTS demonstrates strong performance in some environmental and social aspects—such as labor rights, chemical use, and water quality—its limited engagement with for example air quality, local communities and consumer well-being accounts for the partial or absent coverage. These are areas where schemes operating in broader bioeconomy contexts may need to provide greater detail.

Finally, in Function III, 3 of the 4 principles were fully covered, and 1 was partially covered, indicating the presence of a relatively mature monitoring and evaluation system. While GOTS demonstrates a strong foundation in performance tracking and adaptive learning, the forthcoming Baseline Study for GOTS 7.0 will be a critical step in establishing quantifiable metrics for demonstrating measurable progress and in formalizing stakeholder feedback mechanisms.

This demonstration validated the framework's conceptual soundness and practical applicability. It confirmed that the proposed structure is capable of differentiating between applicable and non-applicable principles while allowing for meaningful comparisons across diverse

certification schemes. The analysis of GOTS highlights both areas of strong alignment—particularly in governance performance—as well as areas that warrant attention, such as circularity and economic indicators. By applying the framework in practice, this case study illustrates how the monitoring system can be used not only as a diagnostic tool but also as a strategic instrument for identifying strengths, gaps, and opportunities for continuous improvement. The insights derived from this pilot assessment inform targeted recommendations for refining the framework (as will be discussed in the following section) and emphasize its potential for broader use across certification schemes operating in complex bio-based value chains.

4. Discussion

Given the increasing global focus on bioeconomy strategies, the need to monitor progress and new developments within bio-based value chains has become crucial (Korosuo et al., 2024). Our findings highlight several gaps in current monitoring efforts for CSLs, particularly regarding their structure, functionalities, and performance assessment. To address these limitations, the proposed monitoring framework—tailored specifically for the complexities of bio-based value chains—adopts a holistic, three-function approach, targeting: (i) building trust and transparency, (ii) protecting sustainability areas of concern, and (iii) driving continuous improvement.

The developed framework incorporates principles aimed at building trust and transparency, recognized as fundamental for ensuring the operational robustness of CSLs (Osmundsen et al., 2020). These principles encompass various themes, such as governance mechanisms, stakeholder engagement, and compliance verification. By providing clear and reliable information to all stakeholders, this trust-building function helps to mitigate concerns about greenwashing and inconsistent claims, thereby reducing confusion and instilling consumer confidence (Majer et al., 2022). Moreover, this component promotes balanced stakeholder representation and influence - an aspect identified as critical for the effective performance of schemes (McDermott, 2013; van der Ven, 2022), particularly in addressing the barriers faced by smallholders in the certification process (Reich and Musshoff, 2025; Schoneveld et al., 2019). Larger producers are more likely to adopt CSLs (Sun, 2022), leading to disparities between large and small economic operators. To address this, the proposed framework monitors inclusiveness in governance mechanisms, standard-setting processes, and stakeholder participation criteria, aiming to bridge this gap by encouraging fair competition, expanding certified areas, and improving market access to smaller entities (Meemken, 2020).

Beyond governance, the framework incorporates a comprehensive set of pillars under Function II, spanning environmental, social, economic, and circular dimensions, aligned with recent contributions to sustainability metrics in the bioeconomy (Ares-Sainz et al., 2025). Notably, balancing the different dimensions of sustainability has been a priority in reducing existing trade-offs between social, economic, and environmental outcomes of CSLs (Vanderhaegen et al., 2018). This approach also aligns with the call for greater transparency of international biomass supply chains, as pointed out by Wang et al. (2023), particularly concerning the negative effects of the land-use emissions. This is a critical issue given that the EU-27 remains one of the largest global importers of biomass for non-food purposes.

Building on experience with existing benchmarking methodologies, the framework also emphasizes the importance of continuous improvement in CSLs. This function involves measuring achieved outcomes through mechanisms such as stakeholder feedback, updated sustainability criteria and refined impact metrics. Regular revisions ensure that CSLs remain adaptive to emerging challenges and regulatory changes. This iterative approach aligns with the principles of reflexive governance, as theorized by Meadowcroft and Steurer (2018), which highlight the importance of dynamic feedback loops for addressing evolving sustainability challenges in the bioeconomy. Indeed, such

Fig. 6. Coverage of applicable principles by the Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS).

systems are instrumental in supporting reflexive guidance, allowing continuous feedback to inform and refine policies and regulatory frameworks.

Taking into account the fast-evolving nature of the bioeconomy sector and its emergent challenges, the framework was conceived as a dynamic tool, rather than a fixed set of criteria. This approach facilitates quick responsiveness and adaptability to this dynamic environment. Hence, in addition to the main functions, the framework incorporates the following features:

- A multi-level structure, allowing principles and indicators to be updated or expanded as new priorities within the bio-based value chains emerge;
- A risk-based approach, which prioritizes high-impact bioeconomy areas such as transparency on transnational value chains and biomass flows, land-use competition, circularity, and inclusion of all relevant stakeholders;
- A balanced evaluation structure, combining both threshold and improvement evaluation models, to enable performance benchmarking while fostering progressive advancements within the bioeconomy sector.

The benchmarking exercise of GOTS against the framework provided tangible insights into its operational strengths and limitations. The application of the framework to the mentioned scheme demonstrated its ability to distinguish between broadly relevant principles and those that are context-specific, confirming the importance of the applicability assessment as a precursor to meaningful evaluation. This step not only ensures methodological fairness but also supports sectoral flexibility without compromising comparability.

The exercise therefore validated the framework's practical applicability and its potential to guide comprehensive assessments of CSLs. It showed that even well-established schemes like GOTS exhibit varying levels of alignment across the three functional areas. Notably, gaps were identified in the coverage of economic and circularity indicators—highlighting thematic blind spots common to many sector-specific schemes. The findings also suggested a need for the framework to accommodate evolving thematic areas that may fall outside traditional environmental or social scopes.

Accordingly, one key recommendation is to maintain the modularity of the framework, allowing schemes to engage with different sets of indicators depending on their scope while ensuring alignment with overarching sustainability goals. Moreover, the framework's structured evaluation across governance, sustainability content, and impact functions enables targeted feedback for scheme owners - identifying strengths (e.g., strong assurance systems or stakeholder engagement) and pinpointing areas for capacity building and continuous improvement (e.g., quantifiable impact tracking, integration of feedback loops).

This study offers concrete implications for various stakeholder groups. For policymakers, the framework can inform adaptive policies that respond to evolving sustainability demands. Considering that CSLs often lack legal endorsement as binding compliance tools - limiting their potential to drive systemic change (Vogelpohl and Töller, 2021), the proposed monitoring framework facilitates the integration of CSLs into legislative frameworks (Moosmann et al., 2020), creating a co-regulatory system that combines governmental oversight with independent initiatives. Such a co-regulatory approach enhances policy effectiveness (Majer et al., 2023), relying more on cooperation with private efforts than on traditional command-and-control regulation (Kolcava and Bernauer, 2021), as demonstrated by the application of certification systems to meet Renewable Energy Directive (RED) criteria (Gaebler, 2014). By bridging regulatory gaps, the framework thereby enables CSLs to act as co-regulatory tools, aligning policies more closely with market practices. Moreover, the monitoring framework can serve policymakers as a tool for assessing the credibility, robustness, and performance of CSLs. It provides clarity on their achievements and

shortcomings, thereby facilitating the continuous improvement of bioeconomy-related strategies and their associated policies - especially important given that a bio-based economy is not inherently sustainable.

The proposed monitoring framework also supports CSLs owners by promoting the continuous improvement of their systems through the identification of low-performing elements and the expansion of their targets. Furthermore, alignment and cooperation among CSLs are also relevant for addressing global environmental challenges (Nakaishi and Chapman, 2024); therefore the framework can serve as an initial step towards the harmonization and mutual recognition of CSLs by highlighting common sustainability and governance objectives across different schemes, encouraging more widespread use.

For businesses, the proposed framework offers a structured system to substantiate and enhance the credibility of sustainability claims. In a context where accusations of greenwashing can harm reputations, the framework equips businesses to align their practices with sustainability goals and regulatory expectations, even addressing unintended misalignments. By fostering transparency and accountability, the framework builds consumer trust and supports adherence to corporate social responsibility commitments. It also prepares businesses to meet evolving regulatory demands, aligning with the findings of Aguinis and Glavas (2012), who underscore the importance of robust assessment tools in competitive, sustainability-driven markets.

Finally, the proposed framework can serve as a tool to enhance sustainable consumption practices by building trust among consumers (Ladu and Morone, 2024). As prior studies have highlighted, consumers have limited access to information about products' environmental and social performance (Delmas and Gergaud, 2021). In addition, the proliferation of CSLs has led to confusion among consumers and concerns regarding their credibility and legitimacy (Derx and Glasbergen, 2014), resulting in decreased adoption. The present framework, with its three assessment elements, aims to provide trustworthy data, reduce information asymmetry, and reinforce transparency and accountability for bio-based products. Consequently, it offers an opportunity to leverage the growing consumers' willingness to pay for certified sustainable goods.

5. Conclusions

This study introduces a conceptual monitoring framework designed to assess the robustness and effectiveness of CSLs operating within complex and evolving bio-based value chains. The proposed framework responds to critical gaps in the current certification landscape—namely, fragmented verification practices, thematic imbalances, and limited mechanisms for continuous improvement—by offering a structured, multidimensional, and adaptable tool that supports more sustainable production and consumption patterns in the bioeconomy.

The conducted analysis of existing benchmarking methodologies and monitoring tools provided crucial recommendations for creating a tailored monitoring framework for bio-based value chains. This framework should be developed in three phases: determining the audience and purpose, deciding which elements to include, and establishing the evaluation structure. The framework incorporates assessments across key performance areas, encompassing not only sustainability indicators but also governance, operational management, and the broader impacts of schemes and labels. Therefore, the three primary functions included in the proposed conceptual framework are: Building Trust and Transparency, Protecting Sustainability Areas of Concern, and Driving Continuous Improvement. Each function not only supports market growth for bio-based products but also fosters a reflexive governance approach in sustainability certification.

Ensuring that the indicators within the monitoring framework are well-defined and transparent, the framework enables a holistic and comprehensive evaluation of CSLs. Furthermore, enhancing connectivity between functional levels (i.e. the three functions proposed in the monitoring system framework) will improve the benchmarking process.

Facilitating the introduction of new principles and thematic areas in response to emerging sustainability issues and evolving industry requirements will enable the monitoring framework to stay up to date with the latest developments and trends in bio-based value chains, ensuring its relevance and effectiveness in promoting sustainability.

The applicability demonstration using the Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS) affirmed the framework's utility across different scheme types and revealed actionable insights for refining both the tool and the schemes it evaluates. It highlighted the importance of maintaining flexibility to accommodate scheme-specific scopes, while also encouraging greater ambition in underrepresented areas such as circularity and economic dimension. This underscores the framework's potential to serve not only as a diagnostic mechanism but also as a strategic instrument for capacity-building, harmonization, and policy alignment across the sector. Looking ahead, further research is needed to update principles, collect longitudinal data, and pilot the framework across a broader array of schemes. These efforts will enrich the benchmarking landscape and offer empirical evidence for improving certification practices in line with evolving EU sustainability goals.

As the bioeconomy expands and diversifies, the proposed monitoring framework can serve as a scalable and adaptive tool for certifiers, businesses, and policymakers alike. Future applications should focus on benchmarking a broader set of schemes across various bio-based sectors and geographies, which will help validate the framework's robustness, reveal cross-cutting gaps, and inform the development of a harmonized sustainability architecture capable of supporting both regulatory and voluntary pathways in global value chains.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Luana Ladu: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Nikola Matović:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Enrica Imbert:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Ana Gabriela Encino-Munoz:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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The BMT is composed of the following three levels: system, content and outcome level. STAR4BBS coordinated the system level, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED coordinated the content-level, and HARMONITOR coordinated the outcome-level. Each of the parties owns the intellectual property of the respective levels. The authors also thank the cluster for

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2025.126240>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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